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Factors of Delinquent Juvenile Behaviors and Education: Psychological and Sociological Theories and Influence of Family

***Ferit Hysa*¹, *Selema Allamani*²**

¹ *University College "Dardania", Prishtina, Kosovo, ferithysa@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2672-1319>*

² *University College "Dardania", Prishtina, Kosovo, selema_i@yahoo.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-6201-3067>*

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Abstract: This study is in the field of sociology, and psychology, and deals with the delinquent behavior of juveniles in Kosovo and Albania and the aim of this study is to discover the main causes of delinquency among juveniles in Kosovo and Albania. The research question raised in this research is: how does family culture affect juvenile delinquency in the context of family culture in Kosovo and in the context of family culture in Albania? Meanwhile, the hypothesis in this study is: that the cultural level of the family affects the increase in juvenile delinquency. The population of this study is the families in Kosovo and Albania. The method is qualitative and quantitative. Data will be collected through structured and semi-structured questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups. An important conclusion of this study is that the family is an excellent model of children's careers and society must compensate for the lack and gaps that families have in the education of children.

Keywords: delinquency, family, culture, education, psychology, sociology.

Introduction

This study aims to study the causes and factors that influence children's delinquency. Delinquency of children is a family and social concern which brings many consequences and difficulties in the perspective of the delinquent child. This study aims to identify the influencing factors in the delinquency of children and especially of juveniles, the construction of strategies for their education. The objectives of this study are i) the identification of the categories of delinquent behavior of minors and ii) the identification of factors that influence the delinquency of juveniles in the case of Kosovo society, as well as iii) the specifics of the Kosovar family in the prevention of delinquency juveniles.

Children's education is an important issue for the family and society in order for children to grow up healthy and be able to build their lives, become successful professionals, provide income for their well-being, and become responsible citizens in society. The delinquency of juveniles complicates and complicates the perspective of children for a safe future. Therefore, the analysis of juvenile delinquency, and the factors that favor it, is very important for the children themselves, their families, and society.

The delinquency of juveniles in Kosovo has its own specifics. An important influence is the Kosovar Albanian family, the consolidation of which has gone through historical challenges. The Kosovar Albanian family has had to face invasions, oppression, and insecurity for centuries. She has created her own tradition of survival in the family and social organization. In these challenges, the Kosovar Albanian family and the Kosovar Albanian Society have their own culture, organization, and tradition. In this context, the delinquency of juvenile children has its own specifics, its positive and negative sides.

Juvenile delinquency has been treated in depth and widely by different researchers. Studies related to delinquency are summarized in these important theories that explain the phenomenon of delinquency. There are many variables and factors that influence juvenile delinquency, therefore juvenile delinquency is explained through several theories of juvenile delinquency. Social, economic, and cultural conditions are constantly changing. In these changes, new influencing factors are constantly created in the delinquency of juveniles or special influences from their combination. Below we describe the main theories of juvenile delinquency.

Any idea about the causes, extent, and correlates of juvenile delinquency is essentially a theory, such as equating juvenile delinquency with sin and violating God's law (DeLisi, 2009). Anomie Theory according to Robert K. Merton based on the state of anomie develops a deviant behavior characterized by rebellions, retreat, ritualism, innovation, and conformity where crime results predominantly from innovation (Wickert, 2022).

Psychological theories explain children's delinquency based on their internal construct that interacts with the social world. Psychologist B.F. Skinner (1953) as a behavioral psychologist that he is, explains delinquency with the stimulus-response theory. He says that children learn conformity and deviance from reinforcements and punishments. Similar to this theory is the theory of social learning. According to Albert Bandura (1977), social learning theory, explains that children learn by modeling and imitating others.

Strain theory is based on the idea that delinquency results when individuals are unable to achieve their goals through legitimate channels. In such cases, individuals may turn to illegitimate channels of goal

achievement or strike out at the source of their frustration in anger (Agnew, 1985). Three major types of strain theory are described: (1) strain as the actual or anticipated failure to achieve positively valued goals; (2) strain as the actual or anticipated removal of positively valued stimuli; and (3) strain as the actual or anticipated presentation of negatively valued stimuli (Agnew, 1992).

Methodology of the study

In this study, the research methodology was used, quantitative and qualitative methods. In this study, by means of the quantitative method, the results of the study can be more precisely defined and the conclusions come out more clearly. The hypothesis of the study is: juvenile delinquency is influenced by a complex of factors. The collection of data is carried out through questionnaires for the causes and factors that help and influence the delinquency of young people. The questionnaires are built according to the Likert scale type based on 5 options from completely disagree to completely agree. The content of the questionnaires is based on two main variables. The first independent variable is the delinquency of children, while the dependent variable is the factors that influence the delinquency of children. The data of the study will be presented in tables and graphs through the Excel program. The discussion of the results will be based on the results of the study.

The qualitative method has to do with the qualitative analysis of the results. The questionnaire also includes open questions which are analyzed according to the method of coding the results of the answers as well as the best interpretation of the open questions for answers.

The study population consists of parents and educators resident in the city of Pristina, one of the largest cities in Kosovo. Pristina's 2023 population is now estimated at 213,162. In 1991, the population of Pristina was 199,654. Pristina has grown by 0.58% annually. These population estimates and projections come from the latest revision of the UN World Urbanization Prospects. The sample of the study consists of 70 people who were chosen freely in the community, with the condition that they were over 15 years old, they had to be residents of the city of Prishtina and they agreed to fill out the questionnaire. The participants were informed of the purpose of the questionnaire, that the data would be confidential, that their publication would be anonymous, and that they could withdraw from completing it even if they had started to complete it. Each participant in completing the questionnaire was free to complete or not the descriptive open question. No identifying mark is placed in the questionnaire.

Research results

The study sample consists of 72 participants. Participation in the study sample consists of 13.9% men and 86.1% women.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Regarding age, the composition of the sample has a majority of about 50% aged over 21-30 years, which guarantees the accuracy of the answers as it is the most qualified age in Prishtina and the age most interested in a clear career perspective of them and a healthy society for their life in the future.

Figure 3

This table presents the results of the public's perception of which are the most problematic behaviors that are more dominant among juveniles.

In this chart, the perception of the public is that over 70% think that the problematic behavior of juveniles is increasing. This is a clear indicator that responsible institutions should take measures to minimize these factors.

Figure 4

Figure 5

According to the results of the study, the main factor in children's delinquency is society.

Figure 6

The data of the study show that the family is not a factor in the creation of children's delinquency. This shows more about the care shown by the regular Kosovar family for the education of the children, but not that the family is not a factor in the increase of children's delinquency.

Figure 7

From the data of the study, charter 7, the school is not seen as a factor in the creation of delinquency, so the school is seen as a factor in the elimination of delinquency.

Figure 8

Discussions

The delinquent behavior of children remains a concern for the community. According to Chart 4, the number of delinquent behaviors among children is increasing. The data is 82% think that the delinquency of children is increasing, 14% think that it is decreasing and 12.5% think that it is remaining the same.

There are many types of delinquent children's behavior. and according to the study data, Chart 3, the most important are: running away from home and school 80%; thefts 74%; beats 71%; drug uses 68%;

disruption of public order and peace 64%; an attack on other persons 58%; possession of weapons without a permit 54%; robbery 51%; risk of trafficking 49%; and bodily injury 47%. All these delinquent behaviors of children and others have their influencing and specific factors. This high perception shows that educational work with children should be programmed and professional by every responsible institution, society, and family.

The problematic behavior of children is influenced by society

Society has a great influence in creating delinquent behaviors in children. According to the social theory of learning (Bandura, 1977) society's models are imitated and used by young people and applied in society. From the data of the study, table 5, and Chart 5, 64% think that society influences the formation of problematic behaviors in children. Society influences not only with negative and positive models, but society is responsible for participating in decision-making to decide on the election agenda of problematic behaviors. The more positive models society presents, the more active it is in condemning problematic behaviors, and the fewer problematic behaviors young people will have.

Children's problem behavior is influenced by the family

The family is important in the formation of young people and the elimination of problematic behaviors. A special aspect of the Kosovar society is that the society has high demands for the education of the children from the family, and the Kosovar family itself feels very responsible and obliged for its obligations for the education of the children. From the data of the study, in Chart 6, it can be seen that the majority think that the family is not at all influential in creating problematic behaviors. So in Kosovar society, the family continues to be consolidated and to be responsible for the education of children so that they do not demonstrate problematic behavior. As in society, the models of parents influence the behavior of children. As Bandura (1977) says, the family is part of society and negative or positive family models influence the problematic behaviors of children. What we can highlight is that the commitment and responsibility for children's education is high, although there may be problems due to the parents' lack of ability to educate them in the right way. The effect of deviant peer groups and deviant parents during adolescence is quite similar. Both peer groups and parents have an important position in the teenager's life; the researcher also found that slum neighborhoods, fragile personalities, and poverty play critical roles in delinquency (Alduraywish, 2021, p. 421).

Children's problem behavior is influenced by school

The school is the most trusted and credible institution for the education of children. Even in Kosovo, the reliability of educational institutions for the education of children is high. From the data in Chart 7, it can be seen that the Kosovar society does not believe that the school affects the problematic behaviors of children, but it affects the reduction of problematic behaviors of children. An element of the social theory of learning is that delinquent behavior is learned. Delinquent behavior to be learned is not demonstrated at school. Kosovar society has high credibility for the school as a responsible institution for the education of children.

Factors affecting juvenile delinquency

The history of children's delinquency is as early as humanity itself. The problems it brings to the personal life of the individual and the complications it brings to society have increased the interest of educators

and researchers to discover the causes and determine the ways of educating children. The developments of society and economic dynamics have brought different contexts and factors with different influences on children's delinquency. Looking carefully at all the theories of delinquency and children's delinquency, it finds that the factors that influence delinquency are complex, with varying power of influence, as well as the creation of new factors simultaneously with economic and social development. Different societies make a group of special factors have more influence than in another society due to tradition, economic factors, and the specific context of society. Such a context is also observed in Kosovar society. According to the data of the study, the factor with a great impact on the delinquency of children is the family. The family factor is 68% in Charter 8, a high figure compared to other factors. This shows that the Kosovar society has high demands on the family in the education of children and prevention of delinquency. At the same time, the Kosovar family feels and bears responsibility for the children's education. She feels responsible to society for the behavior of her children. Another important factor that affects the child's delinquency is the economic factor. According to the study data in charter 8 is 67%, a high figure that shows the influence of this factor on children's delinquency. Theories of delinquency show that the different factors and contexts in children's delinquency have a very complex and varied impact. All theories of child delinquency independently or interwoven with one another identify and predict the sources of child delinquency. The different contexts and power of these factors must be taken into consideration in determining the effective education of children and the interaction of society for the prevention, minimization, and elimination of delinquency.

Delinquency of children in Kosovar society compared to delinquency in Albania.

Child delinquency is a phenomenon not only in Kosovar society and in Albania, but in every country, developed or not, in a democratic society or a totalitarian regime, but with its own specifics according to the context and space to develop. In Albania, educational institutions were developed earlier than in Kosovo and they were developed to respond to the population's demands for education. This has come since 1908 when the first Albanian school for the preparation of the first educators for the education of young people was founded. All Albanians in Albania and Kosovo benefited from this school. After the Second World War, Kosovo remained outside the borders of Albania and therefore the conditions and contexts of the development of education changed a lot. Therefore, the contexts and factors of delinquency were different. In Albania, educational institutions were continuously developed and reflected the needs and wishes of the population for education. While in Kosovo, the educational institutions were built by the governing countries and not at all in accordance with the aspirations of the Albanian people in Kosovo. Under these conditions, the Albanian family in Kosovo takes over the basic part of the children's education in education and behavior. Therefore, the Kosovar family culture has a special impact on the treatment of children's delinquency and is more responsible than society towards this phenomenon.

Conclusion

From the analysis of the data of the study, it appears that the Kosovar society thinks that regarding the delinquent behavior of children, the family bears the main responsibility. This comes as a result of the tradition of the Kosovar society that has been occupied for a long time and has supported children's

education and development in the family and not in public or state institutions. Also, from the data of the study, it appears that the society with its models is also responsible for the delinquent behavior of children.

One of the basic causes of children's delinquency in the family turns out to be the lack of family culture. Regarding the family culture, it is noticed that in many cases we have restrictions on children's freedom, lack of their evaluation, lack of normal communication with them, imposition of parents' opinions as well as lack of dealing with children but leaving them alone without counseling. and the necessary orientation. However, the lack of a positive family model has an important influence on the delinquent behavior of children. Traumas and violence in the family often leave consequences for children and impose negative models of their formation.

The low economic level of the family is another factor of the impossibility of educating children. Children should not only grow physically, but should be oriented towards full education to be able to solve their economic problems in a legal way.

An important factor turns out to be the society with its positive models. The association of children with children with delinquent behavior and other negative models of society negatively affect children's behavior. According to the social theory of learning, behavior is learned, learning is achieved through interactions, criminal techniques are learned, etc. (Bandura, 1977).

One of the factors responsible for the delinquent behavior of children are the educational institutions. In Kosovar society, these institutions are new, democratically elected and accountable to the public. Therefore, these institutions should be developed by addressing the delinquent behaviors of children, analyze their causes and build strategies for the good education of children and the elimination of delinquent behaviors. The family is very important for the education of children, but it should be helped by educational institutions for an education on a scientific and professional basis.

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